

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(V), and Simultaneous Determination of Vanadium(V) and Iron(III), as Mixed-Ligand Complexes with N-Hydroxy-N,N'-diphenyl-*p*-toluamidine and Thiocyanate

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A simple, rapid and sensitive method has been developed for the extractive photometric determination of vanadium(V), and vanadium(V) and iron(III) simultaneously. It is based on the mixed-ligand complex formation of the metals with N-hydroxy-N,N'-diphenyl-*p*-toluamidine (HDPTA) and thiocyanate under same conditions. The ternary complexes have well separated adsorption maxima. The composition of an unknown mixture of these elements can be determined by solving the simultaneous equations.

N-HYDROXY-N,N'-diphenyl-*p*-toluamidine (HDPTA), a newly synthesised reagent, possessing the monobasic and bidentate hydroxyamidine functional grouping¹⁻¹⁰ reacts with vanadium(V) and iron(III) in presence of thiocyanate to give 1 : 2 : 2 (vanadium : HDPTA : SCN⁻) and 1 : 1 : 2 (iron : HDPTA : SCN⁻) complexes, which can be quantitatively extracted into benzene. The iron (red) and vanadium (deep-green) ternary complexes show maximum absorption at 460 nm ($\epsilon = 10100$) and 610 nm ($\epsilon = 5600$) respectively. The proposed method is sensitive and highly selective, and affords a rapid and accurate determination of iron(III) and vanadium(V) simultaneously at microgram level in synthetic mixtures.

TABLE I—ANALYSIS OF SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Mixture No.	Quantity taken, μg		Quantity found, μg^a	
	[Fe]	[V]	[Fe]	[V]
1	10	150	9.78	149.70
2	50	100	49.90	99.32
3	80	60	79.85	59.54
4	100	20	99.60	19.90

a = an average of 5 determinations

Experimental

N-Hydroxy-N,N'-diphenyl-*p*-toluamidine was prepared by the condensation of equimolar quantities of N-phenyl-*p*-toluamidoyl chloride with N-phenylhydroxylamine in ether medium⁵. The resulting hydrochloride was filtered and treated with dilute ammonia to liberate the corresponding free

base. The free base was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (2 : 1). The compound gave satisfactory results for C, H and N analyses. A 0.1% solution of the reagent in benzene was used for extraction work.

Stock solutions of vanadium(V) and iron(III) were prepared from ammonium metavanadate and pure iron wire (E. Merck) respectively. The solutions were standardised volumetrically^{1,1} and gravimetrically^{1,2} respectively. A 1% aqueous solution of potassium thiocyanate was also prepared.

Absorption spectra were recorded on Carl-Zeiss 'Specord' spectrophotometer. An ECIL spectrophotometer model GS-865 equipped with matched 1-cm cells and a Systronic pH meter Type-322 were employed for measuring the absorbance and pH value respectively.

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade.

Procedure for Vanadium : In a separatory funnel place an aliquot of solution containing 30-200 μg of vanadium(V) and to this, add 5 ml of 1% potassium thiocyanate solution. Adjust the pH at 1.5 ± 0.2 and dilute to 25 ml with water. Introduce 25 ml of 0.1% solution of HDPTA in benzene and equilibrate the two phases for 2 min. Dry the extract over anhydrous sodium sulphate and measure the absorbance at 610 nm against benzene as blank.

Procedure for Vanadium and Iron : To a solution containing 20-160 μg of vanadium and 10-100 μg of

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iron, add 5 ml of 1% potassium thiocyanate solution. Adjust the pH at 1.2 ± 0.2 , keeping the final volume of the aqueous to 25 ml. Extract with 25 ml of benzene solution containing 0.1% HDPTA. Dry the organic phase containing the mixed-ligand complexes over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Measure the absorbance at 460 nm and 610 nm against reagent blank. Determine the concentration of the two metals by solving the appropriate simultaneous equation using the molar absorptivities of V and Fe at 460 and 610 nm.

Results and Discussion

Absorption Spectra : The absorption curves for the reagent and ternary iron and vanadium complexes in benzene are shown in Fig. 1. The vanadium ternary complex possesses absorption maximum at 610 nm. The iron(III)-thiocyanate mixed-ligand complex shows a sharp absorption maximum at 460 nm. The reagent does not absorb significantly in the region 450-700 nm.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra :—

- Fe-HDPTA-SCN⁻ complex ($3.17 \times 10^{-5} M$ Fe) + V-HDPTA-SCN⁻ complex ($5.36 \times 10^{-5} M$ V)
- V-HDPTA-SCN⁻ complex ($5.36 \times 10^{-5} M$ V)
- Fe-HDPTA-SCN⁻ complex ($3.17 \times 10^{-5} M$ Fe)
- △—△—△—0.1% HDPTA in benzene.

Influence of pH : The pH was adjusted with hydrochloric acid (2M) and dilute ammonia. The optimum pH ranges giving constant and maximum absorbance are 1.0-3.5 and 0.5-1.5 for vanadium and iron mixed-ligand complexes respectively.

Amount of Reagent : A 6 and 8 fold molar excess of HDPTA and thiocyanate respectively is adequate

for complete extraction of vanadium. The quantitative transfer of iron to organic phase necessitates a 30 and 120 fold molar excess of HDPTA and thiocyanate respectively. Large excess of HDPTA and thiocyanate has no interfering effect on the determination.

Effect of Time and Temperature : The extracts were found to be stable at least for 35 hr at 27°. No remarkable change in absorbance was observed by variation in temperature of aqueous phase from 20 to 35°. Both the metals were completely extracted into benzene by a shaking of one min.

Molar Absorptivities : The effective molar absorptivities for vanadium and iron ternary complexes are 5600 and 700 $l \cdot mol^{-1} \cdot cm^{-1}$ at 610 nm and 6500 and 10100 $l \cdot mol^{-1} \cdot cm^{-1}$ at 460 nm respectively.

Composition of the Mixed-ligand Complexes : The ratio of vanadium to HDPTA was determined by Job's method of continuous variations¹³ and mole ratio method¹⁴, whereas the ratio of vanadium to thiocyanate was determined by mole ratio and slope ratio methods¹⁵. The stoichiometry of iron mixed-ligand complex was determined by curve fitting method¹⁶. The results suggest the formation of 1 : 2 : 2 (vanadium : HDPTA : SCN⁻) and 1 : 1 : 2 (iron : HDPTA : SCN⁻) complexes under the experimental conditions.

Effect of Foreign Ions : Various ions were added to a sample containing 2.0 ppm of iron and 2.0 ppm of vanadium. The complexes were extracted as described in the recommended procedure and the absorbance values were measured at 460 and 610 nm. Interference was considered to occur if the error in the absorbance exceeded 2%. Chloride, bromide, iodide, nitrate, sulphate, acetate, citrate, tartrate, phthalate, borate, arsenate, selenate, alkali metals and alkaline earths and lanthanoid elements did not interfere. The tolerance limits (in ppm) for the other ions tested were : Zr(IV)80 ; Ti(IV)100 ; Mo(VI)10 ; W(VI)20 ; UO₂(II)600 ; Mn(II)300 ; Ni(II), Co(II)500 ; Cu(II), Al(III)600 ; Cr(III)500 ; Bi(III)600 ; Tl(III)1000 ; Th(IV)800 ; Zn(II) ; Cd(II)600 ; Hg(I), Pb(II)700.

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